

Recent advances in applications of POMs and their hybrids in catalysis

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Samahe Sadjadi

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Polyoxometalates (POMs) and their hybrid systems are green and efficient catalysts which have found a wide range of application, due to their outstanding properties such as high thermal stability, Redox potential, strong Bronsted acidity, non-corrosive nature and sensitivity to electricity and light. They are able to catalyze various organic reactions as well as being involved in photocatalytic processes. In this review, we try to highlight the recent advances (2009-2015) in the applications of POMs both in their actual structural forms and in the form of hybrid/ composite as catalysts in divergent chemical processes including, organic synthesis, biomass conversion, petrochemical processes, fuel cell, photocatalytic degradation.

Keyword

Biomass, Catalysis, Fuel cell, HPA, HPAs, Organic synthesis, PMOs, POMs.